

“User Journey Maps and User Guidance”

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SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT

INDUSAC's main objective is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry Academia collaboration (IAC) mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation. Its aim is to build upon pre-existing IAC mechanisms such as EIT KICs and to facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows to develop solutions that clearly address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries. Of a highly digitalised nature, our project pilots the mechanism's two main components: a methodology developed by applying human-centred design principles and an online platform aimed at connecting stakeholders from the industry-academia ecosystem and at supporting them throughout their co-creation journey.

The INDUSAC methodology provides the guidance and tools needed to power the process, whilst the platform stands as a networking space for stakeholders to connect, as well as a co-creation arena to develop joint solutions. Through the experience of supporting at least 300 transnational co-creation teams throughout project lifetime, the INDUSAC mechanism and its two key components will be successively improved until project end, delivering a tested mechanism ready for replication and upskilling. It is expected for INDUSAC to also create a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including at least 1000 companies, 3000 students and 300 researchers by project end. The INDUSAC counts with a strong interdisciplinary, cross-sectorial and geographically balanced partnership that counts with the needed expertise and network to achieve our project's goals.

ABSTRACT

The report D1.3: " User Journey Maps and User Guidance " is part of Work Package (WP) 1: "Human-centred development of the INDUSAC co-creation methodology" of the project "Quick challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation mechanism for INDUSty-Academia collaborations" (INDUSAC).

The goal of this task involves the creation of user journey maps for companies and students/researchers and their interactions with the INDUSAC methodology. The user journey maps will help to understand the user goals at each step of the methodology. Based on these maps, two guidance packages for companies and students/researchers will be developed. These packages will include relevant process definition points such as project kick-off, milestone reviews and management guidelines.

Based on creativity workshops, creativity sessions and several feedback rounds with the WP1-team, there are now two sets of user guidance packages with corresponding user journey maps.

A seamless user journey and effective user guidance are essential for students and companies to solve challenges, work in collaborative teams, and develop creative solutions through INDUSAC. Clear user guidance can help them navigate through the process and access the resources they need to succeed, leading to mutually beneficial outcomes. A well-designed user journey and user guidance can also bridge the gap between academia and industry, fostering collaboration and innovation.

LIST OF ACRONYMS

BAX	BAX Innovation Consulting SL
BIC	Bydgoszcz Industrial Cluster Tool Valley
CCIPB	Pecs-Baranyai Kereskedelmi es Iparkamara
CIT UPC	UPC Technology Center
CUT	Cyprus University of Technology
EIT	EIT Manufacturing East GmbH
FM	Final meeting
FSTP	Financial Support for Third Parties
INDUSAC	Quick challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation mechanism for INDUSty-ACademia collaborations
INNO	Innoget / INNOVAWIN 2006 SL
JSI	Jožef Stefan Institute
KO	Kick-off meeting
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
MS	Milestone meeting
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
PCA	Predefined Collaborative Approach
WP	Work Package

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I. INTRODUCTION

1. Overview of Task

Based on the baseline report (Baseline Report on Industry-Academia Co-creation Approaches (Bastian et al. 2022)), the methodology of the INDUSAC project has been enhanced to provide comprehensive user journey maps for both students and companies. The baseline report gives an overview of existing co-creation formats and elaborates on the success factors of such collaborations in great detail. 22 essential success factors were found and clustered into five groups identified through a systematic approach: good communication and feedback, information and (technical) support, motivation and commitment, people and team, and structure and organisation. Moreover, insights into motivation, structure, and barriers to an IAC were identified. With the baseline report at hand the design of the user journey maps was based on a broad foundation of knowledge. In addition, detailed guidance packages were created to facilitate the INDUSAC co-creation process. The design and explication of the user journey maps and the guidance packages is detailed within this deliverable.

According to WP1 description from this project's Grant Agreement, in this subtask, user journey maps were developed for the main stakeholders of the INDUSAC platform, including companies and students/researchers. These maps will provide a clear understanding of the users' objectives during the different phases of the methodology. Two guidance packages were developed based on these maps, including process definition, management guidelines and other relevant items.

2. User Journey Maps

The process of the user journey maps involves creating a visual representation of the interactions and experiences with the INDUSAC platform and methodology. Therefore, a creativity session has been held, producing the first draft of the user journey maps. After the initial draft multiple rounds of iterative improvement followed, resulting in the user journey maps presented in this report.

In the INDUSAC project, there are two different user journey maps. On one hand, there is the user journey map for students and researchers as they build a team to solve a challenge. On the other hand, there is a user journey map for the company to propose such challenges to the teams.

The user journey maps show the interactions between the two parties. INDUSAC interactions are also shown.

3. User Guidance

The user guidance is a set of instructions that are provided to the students, researchers, and companies to help them navigate and effectively use the INDUSAC platform. These instructions cover several areas, including process definitions, management guidelines, and user objectives at different phases of the process. The provision of user guidance is critical

to ensure that users can use INDUSAC effectively and efficiently. This is particularly important for students and researchers, which is why a to-do list is provided to guide them through the process of solving the challenge

II. USER JOURNEY MAPS

Collaborative creativity methods were employed when creating the user journey maps. Experts for method development at the Institute for Product Engineering at KIT collaborated in creativity and brainstorming sessions to tap into their collective intelligence. Throughout these collaborative sessions, participants were encouraged to let go of all preconceived ideas and create an open environment where they could freely express their opinions. The primary objective was to generate a diverse range of possibilities without judgement, which enabled further refinement and development of the most promising results for user journeys. The procedure of each workshop that was held to develop the user journey maps is explained below.

1. On-Site Creativity Workshop for User Journeys

A creativity workshop was conducted with three participants to discuss user journeys, with two of them being method experts from the Institute of Product Engineering (IPEK) at KIT and the third being the author. All participants are involved in the INDUSAC project. The participants used sticky notes to effectively create and visualise user journeys during the workshop. The sticky notes, representing the user journey of students and researchers, and the company, were (re)arranged in a sequential manner using a large whiteboard. The actors were highlighted, scenarios and expectations discussed, and the journey phases identified. By creating this visual representation, gaps were identified, and a more cohesive experience was designed. The workshop was conducted in an offline environment.

2. Asynchronous Miro Creativity Session

Afterwards, the results were digitised using a Miro board. This made it accessible to all INDUSAC WP1 partners to give and receive feedback. Part of WP1 are the industry partners BIC, CCIPB, JSI and EIT, as well as representatives of academia with CIT UPC, CUT, and KIT. Each project partner was represented by at least one, but often two representatives. This led to a smooth collaboration as the partners could simultaneously contribute, edit, and comment on the virtual board. This promoted both real-time collaboration and feedback. This iterative approach allowed for the discussion of comments that were unclear in team meetings. Within these discussions, different actions, mindsets, and actions of the actors were discussed and mapped. This process resulted in a collaborative decision on how to proceed with the user journey and which steps to include or exclude. Overall, this resulted in several versions of the user journey, ultimately leading to the user journeys presented within this chapter.

3. The Phases of the User Journeys

There are three swim lanes: Student/Researcher, INDUSAC, and Company. They all go through the five distinct phases on the INDUSAC platform. For each type of user, there is a separate swim line to explain the path of each user group when going through the phases.

The user journey maps are shown in several figures below. The figures show the different phases of the process and the tasks that need to be completed at each phase.

In total, five process steps need to be completed:

- **Planning Phase:** The user becomes aware that the INDUSAC platform exists and learns about its opportunities
- **Onboarding Phase:** Within this phase, the companies start interacting with the platform and publish challenges, for students and researchers, there are no process steps within this phase
- **Search Phase:** This phase is now the first actual phase of action for the students and researchers, they actively inform themselves about the existing challenges, find a challenge of interest and start team formation and challenge application. The evaluation of the applications is done by the companies within this phase.
- **Project Phase:** The challenge is solved by students and researchers within this phase. The company assists with questions and finally evaluates the solution.
- **Offboarding Phase:** Within the final phase feedback is given and the payment and certificate for the students is sent.

Below, there is an overview of the user journey map. In each swim lane, the INDUSAC process for the respective party is depicted as how the parties interact with each other. Figure 1 can be found in the ANNEX 1 in landscape format (Figure 11) for better readability.

Figure 1 : User Journey Map Overview

4. User Journey Students and Researchers

4.1. Planning Phase Students and Researchers

This phase aims to make students and researchers aware of the platform.

4.2. Onboarding Phase Students and Researchers

Students or researchers start directly into the search phase.

4.3. Search Phase Students and Researchers

Figure 2 : Search Phase Students and Researchers

In this phase, teams must complete the following tasks: select a challenge from a specific company, create a user profile, find a team, apply for a challenge, and initiate the project to complete the phase (Figure 2).

4.4. Project Phase Students and Researchers

Figure 3 : Project Phase Students and Researchers

In this phase, students and researchers solve the challenge. The process includes a suggested timeline or to-do list to complete the challenge within the specified timeframe. Milestone meetings will provide the opportunity to collaborate with the company and receive feedback, and guidance.

In the end, they submit their solution and receive notification about the acceptance or rejection of the submitted solution (Figure 3).

4.5. Offboarding Phase Students and Researchers

Figure 4 : Offboarding Phase Students and Researchers

At the end of the challenge, there will be a feedback meeting of the co-creation team. The company will provide feedback on the solution and may offer a letter of recommendation. Students will receive payment from INDUSAC to their designated bank account. Upon completion, a certificate of participation will be issued by INDUSAC through the platform (Figure 4).

5. User Journey Company

5.1. Planning Phase

In the first phase, the company must become aware of a company need on which the teams can work.

5.2. Onboarding Phase

Figure 5 : Onboarding Phase Company

During the onboarding phase, the first step is registering on the platform and creating a company profile, including an account for each company representative. The next step is to create and submit the challenge (Figure 5).

5.3. Search Phase

Figure 6 : Search Phase Company

Once the challenge is published, an online/digital challenge presentation can be hosted and teams wishing to complete the challenge will have until the cut-off date to submit their applications. The companies will then receive an email with links to the applications and instructions on how to select the teams via the platform. If they made their decision, they initiate the project with the selected teams (Figure 6).

5.4. Project Phase

Figure 7 : Project Phase Company

During this phase, the teams solve the challenge independently. However, there are several milestone meetings where the teams and the company collaborate, and the teams get guidance from the company (Figure 7).

Once the teams submitted their solution, the next step is for the company to evaluate the solution.

5.5. Offboarding Phase

Figure 8 : Offboarding Phase Company

After the project is completed, feedback on the INDUSAC process must be provided using the feedback template provided. A feedback meeting with the team to evaluate their solution and provide feedback on the collaboration is also recommended. A letter of recommendation can be provided if desired.

Based on the solutions you have gathered from this challenge; it is possible to use the findings and results as a starting point for a new challenge to build on or improve (Figure 8).

III. USER GUIDANCE

For the two parties concerned, two respective user guides are shown below.

The user guidance for students and researchers mentions a variety of methods, tools and to-do lists tailored to specific Predefined Collaborative Approaches (PCA) as presented in Bastian et al. (2023). Just like a PCA helps a company formulate a challenge, the To-Do lists help the students solve it. Each PCA has a different goal, which is the reason for the To-Do lists being specific to the PCAs as well. There are different recommendations for the time needed to solve a challenge that is written with PCA1 as template in comparison to a challenge written with PCA2 as template. Furthermore, different methods and tools are needed by the students to be able to successfully solve a challenge, the recommended tools and methods also depend on the PCA which has been used to write a challenge. The methods and tools and their explanations as well as the To-Do lists will be available on the INDUSAC platform. These documents have been prepared additionally to the user guidance that follows within this chapter. They have been mentioned here, since they additionally help guide users.

The following subchapters will first explain the detailed user guidance for students and researchers and second, the user guidance for companies.

1. User Guidance Students and Researchers

In this User Guidance, you will learn about the steps of the INDUSAC process. The INDUSAC process consists of five phases: Planning Phase, Onboarding Phase, Search Phase, Project Phase and Offboarding Phase. Each of the phases and the steps are explained below. If some of your questions are not answered here, please consult the FAQ. If you don't find an answer there, send an email to the Help Desk: indusac@ijs.si.

Disclaimer: The process is the same for students and researchers unless explicitly stated otherwise.

1.1. Planning Phase:

If you're a student or researcher interested in INDUSAC, you need to know about it first. INDUSAC has made it easy to get information through different channels like social media ([Twitter](#) and [YouTube](#)), media relations, and [promotional materials](#). In addition, INDUSAC provides a [website](#) and a [platform](#).

To start, you can check out INDUSAC's Twitter and YouTube accounts to get an overview of the project. You can also find information on LinkedIn groups and posts related to INDUSAC. If you actively participate in these groups, you might stumble upon an interesting challenge.

You can also get to know INDUSAC through your university's press releases or by reading articles published by INDUSAC's partners. Some partners have social media accounts

where you can make first contact. INDUSAC has also published scientific publications about the project.

Finally, you could attend events where INDUSAC has flyers, rollups and other promotional material to help you find out more.

1.2. Onboarding Phase:

As a student or researcher, you start directly into the search phase which will be explained in detail in the next part (Search Phase).

1.3. Search Phase:

During this phase, you will select a challenge from a particular company, set up your user profile, find your team, apply for a challenge, and complete the phase by initiating the project.

You start this phase by selecting a challenge. If you are a student or researcher, you can go to the [INDUSAC platform](#) or the [INDUSAC website](#). On both websites, you'll find the challenges published by companies. You can filter them by country name, type of challenge, company sector (1st level of NACE codes), and free text search among the public parts of all challenges (name of the company, the title of the PCA, description of the PCA, web page of the company, predefined keywords), and active/inactive projects. The titles and a picture will be included in the list of challenges on the website. If you want to know more about the challenge, you can click on the challenge and find out more. The challenge description will give a broad problem description, the context of the problem your team needs to solve, but also the expectations of the company and in some cases the desired team profiles. You can also find out more about the company posting the challenge. To do this, click on the company's profile name and you will be taken to the company's profile on the platform.

If the information provided on the websites is not sufficient, or if you would like to ask additional questions, you may be able to attend an additional (but optional) challenge presentation by the companies. If the company offers a challenge presentation, it will be shown on the challenge site.

Once you have selected a challenge that interests you, you can begin the process of finding potential teammates. To do this, visit the third-party communication platform [Slack](#) and access the link to the Slack channel for the specific challenge you're interested in. This link is provided in the challenge posting. Within the channel, express your interest in the challenge and outline the skills you have that could contribute to its completion. In addition, take some time to review what other students or researchers who have expressed interest in the challenge have posted. By evaluating the information provided by each individual, you can begin to identify potential team members who might be a good match for you. It's important to note that all teams must meet certain requirements, so keep this in mind as you proceed. The requirements are explained in more detail in the INDUSAC Call for students and researchers. After identifying potential team members, you can start a

conversation with them to see if they would be a good fit for your team. Once you feel confident in your choices, you can create your own Slack channel to discuss your team's goals, objectives and other relevant details. Within this chat, you can begin working on the project associated with your challenge application.

Once you have found your team, go back to the INDUSAC platform and register. To do this, create the appropriate user account (each student or researcher must have an account) and fill in all the required information. The mandatory fields are marked with an asterisk and will be publicly visible.

Once all team members are registered on the platform, you can apply for a challenge. To apply for a challenge, you need to submit a common motivation. In this document, your team must explain why you are interested in this topic, what skills you might have to solve this challenge, and a general letter of motivation. Make sure to fill in the fields as accurately as possible as they are evaluation criteria (Impact score, Excellence score, Implementation score, and Transversal criteria). For details look at the INDUSAC Call for students and researchers.

In the next step, you select one person in your team to be the team leader. This person will be the one to apply for the challenge. In this step, the selected person will upload your team's motivation for the challenge and add all team members to the challenge in the application form. To apply, the team leader accepts the legal terms and conditions and applies for the challenge. The other members of the co-creation team will receive an email for the challenge application and must also accept the legal terms.

INDUSAC will then receive your application and check that you are eligible and that you meet all the criteria for co-creation teams. If the decision is positive, the company will receive and evaluate your application.

Once the company has made its decision, you will be notified over the INDUSAC platform. If the response is negative, your application process will stop. If the response is positive, your process continues and will lead to the initiation of the project. The company must explain either decision.

At this stage, you (**only students**) will need to provide your bank details, as only you will be entitled to receive the grant once the process has been completed. You will also have to sign a contract with INDUSAC. The signing process will be done electronically. Optionally, all team members have to sign a contract with the company (e.g. NDA, etc.) if they wish to provide you with one.

Additionally, you will evaluate the current level of particular skills before the start of the project.

1.4. Project Phase:

Once all the documents have been signed, you start your project with a team meeting to meet the company. INDUSAC will provide you with a list of deliverables, methods and tools

required to address the challenge. A suggested timeline or to-do list will also be provided to ensure that the challenge is addressed within the specified timeframe. Throughout the process, you will have the opportunity to collaborate with the company and receive feedback and guidance at milestone meetings. This will allow you to obtain additional information and support as needed to complete the challenge. The timeframe for completing a challenge is four to eight weeks. The person we call a company representative within the to-do list is the person responsible for your challenge from the company's side. Throughout the process you and the companies might be approached by INDUSAC partners to discuss if you are progressing as planned and if you need any additional guidance.

Once you have solved the challenge and prepared all the deliverables, including the project report, upskilling questionnaire, feedback on the INDUSAC process and testimonial, your team leader will submit the solution via the platform. There are specific fields for each deliverable. If you have files that are too large to upload, please contact the company and agree on how to share the results.

INDUSAC will then receive your solution and check it for eligibility and whether you have met all the criteria for the deliverables. If the decision is positive, the company will receive and evaluate your solution.

Once the company has made its decision, you will be notified. If the response is negative, your challenge process will be terminated without payment (only for students, researchers don't receive payment in any case). If the response is positive, your process continues and leads to the next step "Feedback and Learning".

1.5. Offboarding Phase:

To complete the process you will have a feedback meeting with your co-creation team.

You will receive feedback from the company on your solution. Optionally, they will write you a letter of recommendation.

After this step, you (**students only**) will receive the payment from INDUSAC to the bank account you indicated during the project initiation.

Finally, you will receive a certificate of participation from INDUSAC through the platform.

Figure 9 : Exemplary timeline for Students and Researchers

In Figure 9 you can see an exemplary timeline of a project process. The process consists of a kick-off meeting (KO), followed by up to four project phases with respective milestone

meetings (MS1, MS2). In each project phase, you will work on different tasks which will support you in preparing your solution. The process is finalised with a final milestone meeting (FM) where you present your results. Your challenge ends with the submission of your results.

2. User Guidance Company

In this User Guidance, you will learn about the steps of the INDUSAC process. The INDUSAC process consists of five phases: Planning Phase, Onboarding Phase, Search Phase, Project Phase and Offboarding Phase. Each of the phases and the steps are explained below. If some of your questions are not answered here, please consult the FAQ. If you don't find an answer there, send an email to the Help Desk: indusac@ijs.si.

2.1. Planning Phase:

If you want to post a challenge on the INDUSAC platform, it can be done with almost any question you could use creative input on. Is there a task where an outside view can provide the necessary input? Are you stuck on a question, and you just can't find a new idea? Would you benefit from outside assistance in carrying, for example, market analysis? New product or service ideas, new business models, solutions to solve given customer needs and much more can be developed for you by INDUSAC teams. If your need for the company is identified, you can start preparing.

2.2. Onboarding Phase:

First, you need to register on the platform. You can create a company profile and an account for each company representative. To do this, create the appropriate user account (company account or company representative) and fill in all the required information. The mandatory fields are marked with an asterisk. To successfully register, you must accept the legal terms and conditions. The company account is just like a LinkedIn profile of your company, giving more details about what you do and what you stand for. The purpose of a company representative account is to give the contact person for the students a face. Cooperation is always easier if you know who sits behind the computer on the other side.

The next step is to create your Challenge. To do this, click on "Add Challenge" on the INDUSAC platform and you will be taken to your challenge page. INDUSAC provides 9 themed templates that you can use to create your challenge. The templates are designed to give you a guide to provide students and researchers, who will be solving the challenge with all the information they need. It is also an opportunity for you to check that you have fully thought through the challenge. Once you have chosen an appropriate template (of the 9 possible choices), you will be able to fill in your information. Please note that all challenges will be publicly available and must include only non-confidential information. In all cases, students will sign an agreement with INDUSAC to receive funding (FSTP). If your company requires any additional contracts to sign (e.g. NDA) with students and researchers, you can upload such an agreement in this step.

You can decide how many teams will work on your challenge but remember that there will be milestone meetings at which a company representative should be present to make the challenge a success. Make sure you provide sufficient resources, particularly in terms of your time, to work with the teams. You then submit the challenge, and INDUSAC will receive your challenge and check it for eligibility. If any information is missing, you will receive a notification and can revise the challenge. Once the revisions are completed (or there are no revisions necessary), the challenge will be published, and you will receive an email to the email address you provided during the registration.

2.3. Search Phase:

After the challenge has been published, you have the option to host an online/digital challenge presentation. This allows you to have a first meeting with potential teams interested in your challenge and you will be able to answer questions and go into more detail.

After the cut-off date for the teams that wish to solve your challenge, you will receive an email with links to the applications and instructions on how to select the teams via the platform. Once you have selected or rejected the teams over the platform, they will receive a notification. In case of approval or rejection of a team, you must explain your decision. The next step is the project initiation. If you have a separate contract (e.g. additional NDA, etc.) for the teams, it will be signed at this stage.

2.4. Project Phase:

During the project phase, the students and researchers will solve the challenge. The first step is a collaborative kick-off meeting with the team solving the challenge. In this meeting, you will get to know each other, and you will provide the students and researchers with information about the company and talk about expectations. A meeting can be online or in person at the company's premises.

The team will then work on the challenge independently of the company (except during regular milestone meetings). INDUSAC will provide the teams with a list of deliverables, methods, and tools for the challenge. In addition, the teams will be provided with a suggested timeline (to-do list) to complete the challenge. Throughout the process, the teams should be able to work with you (the company representative) to get more information and receive feedback and guidance in milestone meetings. Working together closely with the teams ensures that they are right on track and meet your expectations. The suggested timeframe to complete a challenge is four to eight weeks. Throughout the process you and the teams might be approached by INDUSAC partners to discuss if you are progressing as planned and if you need any additional guidance.

After the teams solve the challenge, they will submit their solution. You evaluate the solutions following the guidelines and templates and submit the evaluation to INDUSAC.

2.5. Offboarding Phase:

To complete the process, you will need to provide feedback on the INDUSAC process. You will be provided with a feedback template (a questionnaire). We also recommend a feedback meeting with the team to provide them with an evaluation of their solution and feedback on how you perceived working together with them. If you wish, you can write a letter of recommendation for the team.

Based on the solutions you have gathered from this challenge; it is possible to use the findings and results as a starting point for a new challenge to build on or improve.

Figure 10 : Exemplary timeline for Companies

Figure 10 is an exemplary timeline of a project process. The process consists of a kick-off meeting (KO), followed by up to four project phases with corresponding milestone meetings (MS1, MS2). In each project phase, the teams work on different tasks to help them prepare the solution. The process concludes with a final milestone meeting (FM) where the team presents its results. The Challenge ends with the submission of the results.

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, a seamless user journey and effective user guidance can help students and companies achieve their goals of solving challenges, working in collaborative teams, and developing creative solutions. By providing clear user guidance, students, researchers, and companies can easily navigate through the INDUSAC process and access the resources and support they need to succeed.

This collaboration can lead to mutually beneficial outcomes, with students gaining valuable skills, experience and mentorship from industry professionals, and companies gaining access to new ideas, perspectives, and talent. Finally, a well-designed user journey and user guidance can help bridge the gap between academia and industry, fostering collaboration and innovation across sectors.

V. LIST OF REFERENCES

Bastian, Annika; Hellwig, Imke; Kempf, Christoph; Dühr, Katharina (2022): Baseline Report on Industry-Academia Co-creation Approaches. Deliverable D1.1 (Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centred Co-Creation mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations (Horizon Europe project No. 101070297)).

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VI. ANNEXES

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ANNEX 1 : User Journey Maps

Final User Stories

Figure 11 : User Journey Map – landscape format

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